

THE ROLE OF DIALECTS IN FOLK CULTURE

Hakimova Zamira Xurram qizi

First-year doctoral student of the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

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Annotatsiya. *Har bir til o'z shevasiga egaligi haqiqatdir. Barcha o'zbek shevalari ham adabiy tilning shakllanishida u yoki bu darajada ishtirok etadilar. Ammo aynan bittasi asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ya'ni, ma'lum bir shevaning leksik, grammatik, fonetik jihatlari adabiy til uchun asos sifatida qabul qilinadi. Shevalar tinimsiz rivojlanib turadi. Sababi ular jonli tildir va shuning uchun doimo o'zgarib, boyib boradi. Ushbu maqolad shevalarning xalq madaniyatidagi o'rni haqida ma'lumot berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *O'zbek tili, sheva, adabiy til, qadimgi turkey so'zlar, til standarti, Qarluq—chigil-uyg'ur, qipchoq, o'g'uz.*

Аннотация. *Каждый литературный язык имеет свой диалект. Правильно, узбекский. В формировании литературного языка в той или иной степени участвуют все диалекты, но отдельные диалекты служат базой, опорой (основой) для литературного языка, то есть узбекский литературный язык является лексическим от определенных диалекты, принимает фонетические и грамматические особенности как факт литературного языка и тому подобное. Диалект и группа диалектов развиваются по мере своего развития, ведь диалект – это живой язык, он постоянно развивается и меняется. В данной статье представлена информация о роли диалектов в народной культуре.*

Ключевые слова: *узбекский язык, диалект, литературный язык, древнетюркские слова, стандарт, карлук-чигиль-уйгурский, кипчак, огузский.*

Abstract. *Every literary language has its own dialect. That's right, Uzbek in the formation of the literary language, all dialects participate to one degree or another does, but certain dialects serve as a base, support (basis) for the literary language performs, that is, the Uzbek literary language takes lexical, phonetic and grammatical features as a fact of literary language from certain type of dialect. A dialect and a group of dialects evolve, because a dialect is a living language, it is constantly developing and changing. This article provides information about the role of dialects in folk culture.*

Keywords: *Uzbek language, dialect, literary language, ancient Turkic words, standard, Qarluq-Chigil-Uighur, Kipchak, Oghuz.*

The science of dialectology is a branch of linguistics, and it is a local dialect and special features of dialects, their literary language and each other differences from each other, attitude of dialects to literary language, literary language importance in enrichment, networks and groups of dialects, their development learns the history of stages and similar issues. Dialectology Greek derived from the word dialektos, the existing dialects and dialects of a language teaches. Dialect is dialect, logos is doctrine, that is, doctrine about dialect means. Dialect in the scientific literature of Uzbek dialectology, the terms "dialect" and "dialect" are used in different meanings. However, it is the meaning of the terms does not have much difference from each other. The term "Sheva" is a Persian word that means voice, language, speech, habit, yosin, expressing such meanings as idioms, phonetic, lexical and is the smallest part with grammatical features. Dialect (Arabic word and expresses meanings such as expression, word, dialect, voice) these characteristics is a collection of unifying dialects. For example, Oghuz dialect, Kipchak like the dialect. This term is

sometimes used in a narrow sense, that is, in a dialect sense is also used. For example, a few words about the Vodil village dialect such as.

Based on its task, literary language is developed on the basis of dialects: something from that dialect, something from this dialect is taken, and a common form is created that is understandable to everyone. Based on this, it is a mistake to consider the literary standard as the "correct" version of the language. This is just an artificial construct designed to serve society. It should not be considered "correct". Let's not forget that it is a conditional form of language with a concrete task. If we know this, we will put an end to what is considered "correct in the written language and incorrect in the dialect" and the existence of a hierarchy of dialects according to their proximity to the literary language, that is, the position of all dialects is the same. will be If we do this, "which dialect is closer to the literary language?" the argument ends. Dialect is a living, naturally developed form of language, and a literary norm has a specific function, a functional form. If we accept this concept, the status and "correctness" of a dialect is not determined by its proximity to the literary language. The relationship between literary language and dialects is a special problem constitutes Dialects are historically more stable than dialects for literary language the generalization of its representatives from a linguistic point of view becomes more complicated. Nowadays, many countries (for example, Italy, Indonesia, etc.) dialects are used in the same way as literary language. The concept of literary language is usually language is connected with the concept of styles. But this connection is one-sided. Because language methods themselves are literary language forms. They are historically formed, consists of a certain set of characters. Some of these signs are different can be repeated in styles. However, these repeated characters are in a certain form The uniqueness of the combination and function is the difference between one style and another defines. Granting the status of the State language to the Uzbek language (1989) Uzbek literary language was an important development event. The Uzbek literary language is the literary language of different nations is being further improved based on development experience.

F. Abdullaev lexicon of the Oghuz dialect, Azerbaijani and Turkmen he studies the Kipchak dialect and the Uzbek literary language in a comparative way. Instead also refers to the sources of the old Uzbek literary language. Aryg in Khorezm dialects Words like (pok, toza), oram (street), kölk (horse), tuñ (copper pot) are old Uzbek mentions the existence of monuments of literary language in the language. Olim belongs to the Oghuz dialect identified the names of more than forty fish species, only five or six of them emphasizes its existence in the Uzbek literary language. Fish names in research Twenty-five are named and explained. Also, with fishing at work lexical units related to the directly related Oghuz dialect were also analyzed. F. Abdullaev study of the lexicon of Turkic languages in a historical-comparative aspect first of all, related languages, especially living dialects believes that it is necessary to collect more perfect factual materials. Research names of relatives (twin - twin; grandfather - like a baby); members name (ørn — lip; bag`yr — liver; bur`t//mur`t — like a mustache), man and his life, words-terms related to livelihood (alchaq — nimble, capable, uddaburo; ig - pain; İde — like jiyda) adds a dictionary.

A. Ahmedov "Oghuz elements and manifestations in the history of the Uzbek literary language Ughuz elements (elements) and the appearance of Oghuz in the study uses terms and explains the concepts represented by these terms. According to him, Oghuz unsur (elements) are typological of Turkic languages according to its features, it is typical of the Oghuz group, but in the Uzbek literary language In this way, it is a normalized phenomenon. The Oguz form is written in Uzbek in the sources, the Ugz language is side by side with standard Garlug forms is the application of events. Element and appearance are strictly historical concepts. A phenomenon that

appears in a certain period is an element in another period It is possible or an event that is an element in a certain period in another period it can be seen. In particular, the Uygur element of XIII-XVIII in centuries it was an Uzbek appearance, and for the modern Uzbek literary language, this is it Uygur language took the position of an element.

In the modern Uzbek literary language, borrowing words from the dialect is also an internal possibility of the language is considered What was Abdurauf Fitrat's attitude to this issue? Scientist "An experiment on the rules of the Uzbek language: Sarf, Nahv". It is mentioned in the beginning of the Uzbek language textbook expressed his attitude to Uzbek dialects as follows: "We know that our cities have been home to Arabic and Persian literature for hundreds of years lives under the rule. That's why our urban language is corrupt. Our language we can see its pure form in our hands in the field." Scholar Muhabbat Kurbanova Abdurauf Fitrat's work as a fighter for the purity of the Uzbek language is highly evaluated and writes the following: "...In this regard, he (Fitrat) is the greatest of the Uzbek people thinker is second only to Alisher Navoi. Our language of nature His dreams about Hazrat Navoi are in sync with the thoughts of Hazrat Navoi..."

Is dialect important, literary language?

Not only compatriots far from the language, but also intellectuals sometimes get rid of the dialect, calls to speak "correctly" and attempts to narrow the scope of dialects we will see. In general, blind enthusiasm for the literary language, strict adherence to its standards we can show clinging as a trend among today's intellectuals. But if we know that the literary language is conditional, our attitude towards it will be a little easier. Spelling rules must be followed, of course, but the written language will stagnate if not reformed and moves away from spoken language. Therefore, sometimes revising the literary language, it is necessary to adapt to the dialects. For example, when we study in school, it is in English The verb "subject" had two forms used in the future tense - shall and will. After the Shall form has left the spoken language, it is not written in today's textbooks was also removed from the language. This is the language with our conservative approach will not update. A language that is not updated does not become modern, it is modern with its concepts cannot be expressed. Some problems of the Uzbek language today it follows from that. Therefore, dialects do not adapt to the literary language, but the literary language adapts to the dialects must After all, the dialect is the living form of the language and the main source of enrichment of the literary language. Paying attention to the literary language, we sometimes forget the dialects. In fact, in society literary language and dialect should have their place. The dialect contains historical memory, preserves cultural skills and vocabulary. This capital of his literary language should be conducted. Another issue is the proper place of dialect and literary language. there is a scope of importance and consumption. None of them can be completely abandoned. Preservation of dialects in everyday life, folklore, art, TV, Internet, cinema, they should be actively used in music. The role of literary language - in documents, education, in the media. That is why the dialect is used in movies, on some TV channels, and on the Internet I do not consider it a negative situation. Sheva is expanding its scope of consumption, and this is a positive situation.

Every literary language has its own dialect. That's right, Uzbek In the formation of the literary language, all dialects participate to one degree or another does, but certain dialects serve as a base, support (basis) for the literary language performs, that is, the Uzbek literary language is lexical from certain dialects and dialects, takes phonetic and grammatical features as a fact of literary language and that. A dialect and a group of dialects evolve as they evolve, because a dialect is a living language, it is constantly developing and changing. Because of this literary language in connection with the development of this dialect or group of dialects develops, on the contrary, if

the literary language does not have its own dialect, it gradually goes out of circulation. In linguistics, the one that comes out of the conversation is "dead" is called "language". About the existence of "dead languages" in the history of languages there is a lot of information. The Uzbek language is a multi-dialect language. This is its complex historical development The Uzbek nation today is ethnically diverse in the past is determined by having content. The constituent of the Uzbek national language different dialects can be combined into three dialects. These are: 1) Qarluq-Chigiluyghur dialect; 2) Kipchak dialect; 3) Oghuz dialect. Dialects are different feature. Each of these dialects originally belonged to a different tribe or it is related to the fact that it is the language of tribal associations.

Summary: Anyone who wants to learn dialects and dialects on their own he can choose the basis of checking the dialect he is interested in. Linguist go to the place to be inspected and get acquainted with the local conditions and population and observes the dialect. Dialect checkers themselves they pay special attention to the areas of interest and it is unique begin to record the characteristics. The duration of the work of the researcher determined by the goal and plan.

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